

AUTHOR'S GUIDELINES

Center of Language & Cultural Studies, Surakarta, 7 September 2018

SUBMISSION PREPARATION

As part of the submission process, authors are required to check all of the following items, as submissions may be returned to authors that do not adhere to these guidelines.

Please read the **Author Guide** before you submit a manuscript.

- The submission has not been previously published, nor is it before another journal for consideration (or an explanation has been provided in Comments to the Editor).
- The submission file is in Microsoft Word file format.
- The text adheres to the stylistic and bibliographic requirements outlined in the **Author Guide**.
- Add DOIs and persistent links to those references that have DOIs.
- If the paper is accepted for publication, you will be asked to pay an **Article Publication Charge**: IDR 400.000/article.
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Prior to review by the board of editor, each paper is screened by the Member of the Editorial Board to check its suitability for favour of publication. If it can be considered for publication than the Corresponding Author will receive a notification of peer-review process. All manuscripts are reviewed by an editor and members of the Editorial Board or qualified outside reviewers. This is done within the shortest given time. The journal strives to return reviewers' comments to authors within 3 weeks. The editorial board re-review manuscripts that are accepted until they are revised. Papers will be published one to two months after acceptance.

Upon the completion of the review process, an article will receive an evaluation result as follows:

- Accepted
- Accepted with minor revision
- Accepted with major revision
- Rejected or declined

Manuscript Selection

Step 1: Basic Check

The editor or editorial assistant checks a received manuscript to determine whether it fits the journal's aim and scope. Manuscripts out of the journal's scope are rejected. Articles published fully or partly in other publications/websites are not reviewed or accepted.

Step 2: Similarity Check

Please be aware that we check all submitted manuscripts for plagiarism. We use Cross Check (powered by checkforplagiarism.net, the plagiarism-detection system by Google) to check for similarity to previously published documents. All manuscripts containing plagiarism, including self-plagiarism, and dishonesty are rejected.

Step 3: Peer Review

We use a double-blind system for peer review; both reviewers' and authors' identities remain anonymous. The submitted manuscript will be reviewed by at least two experts: one editorial staff member as well as one to three external reviewers. The review process may take two to four weeks. In some rare cases, according to the recommendations from editors and reviewers, a second round of peer review may be initiated.

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The decision to accept an article is based on the average score given by reviewers. The reviewers grade a submitted manuscript on a scale of 1 to 5. To be accepted for publication, the manuscript must obtain an average score not less than 2.5. However, we may reject a manuscript with a score higher than 2.5 when an editor or reviewer thinks it is not suitable for publication.

Charges and Fees

An article that is accepted for publication in this journal will be charged for the Article Publication Charge (APC) IDR 400.000. The contributions are made possible to support a range of publishing services we provide including: provisions of online tools for authors and editors, article production and hosting, liaison with abstracting and indexing services, and customer services. The APC should be paid immediately after notification of article acceptance has been received by the author.

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Please ensure that all corrections are sent back to us in one communication. Please check carefully before replying, as inclusion of any subsequent corrections cannot be

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Ethics Statement

This is the statement of ethics adapted from the principles of the **Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)** and covers the code of ethics for chief editor, editorial board members, reviewers and authors.

DUTIES OF AUTHORS

- Have the responsibility of ensuring only new and original work is submitted.
- Must not reproduce work that has been previously published in other journals.
- Must not submit any articles that are being reviewed or considered by the journal to other journals simultaneously.
- Are only allowed to publish their work elsewhere after receiving a formal rejection from the journal or if their request to withdraw their work is officially accepted by the journal.
- Must inform the Chief Editor or the publisher of any inaccuracy of data in their published work so that correction or retraction of article can be done.
- Should make significant contributions and be held accountable for any shortcoming in their work.

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- Must disclose any competing interest before agreeing to review a submission.
- Can refuse to review any submission due to a conflict of interest or inadequate knowledge.
- Review all submissions objectively, fairly and professionally.
- Reveal any ethical misconduct encountered while reviewing to the Chief Editor for further action.
- Should ensure the originality of a submission and be alert to any plagiarism and redundant publication.
- Must not discuss the content of the submission without permission.
- Adhere to the time allocated for the review process. Requests for extension to review the submission is at the discretion of the Chief Editor.

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- Actively contribute to the development and the greater good of the journal.
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- Review any work assigned to them.

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- Evaluate manuscripts fairly and solely on their intellectual merit.
- Ensure confidentiality of manuscripts and not disclose any information regarding manuscripts to anyone other than the people involved in the publishing process.
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- Give clear instructions to potential contributors on the submission process and what is expected of the authors.
- Ensure appropriate reviewers are selected/ identified for the reviewing process.

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Authors should submit only original work that is not plagiarized, and has not been published or being considered elsewhere. Appropriate softwares may be used by the editorial office to check for similarities of submitted manuscripts with existing literature. Inclusion of fraudulent or knowingly inaccurate statements are unacceptable. Work and/or words from other publications must be appropriately cited or quoted.

REPORTING

Authors should state their results clearly, honestly, and without fabrication, falsification or inappropriate data manipulation. The methods used in the work should be clearly and unambiguously described so that the findings can be repeated and confirmed by other researchers.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

A statement on conflict of interest must be included in the manuscript if authors receive any support that might be construed to influence the results or interpretation of their manuscript. All sources of financial support for the project should be disclosed.

AUTHORSHIP AND COLLABORATION

Name of authors listed in a paper should be limited to those who have made a significant contribution to the report. Only those who have made significant contributions should be listed as co-authors. Others who have participated in certain substantive aspects of the work must be acknowledged or listed as contributors. It is the duty of the corresponding author to ensure that all appropriate co-authors and no inappropriate co-authors are included on the paper. All co-authors must approve the final version of the paper and agree to the version of the paper before submission.

MULTIPLE OR REDUNDANT

Authors should not publish manuscripts describing essentially the same research output in more than one journal or primary publication. A similar manuscript should not be submitted to more than one journal concurrently as this constitutes as unethical publishing behavior and is unacceptable.

GENERAL GUIDELINES TO WRITE MANUSCRIPT

Research Article

Original paper or research paper promoting results of a research, or review paper as a result of review of literature others' researches or opinions have been published.

The general organization of the research paper is presented into IMRAD

- Introduction
- Methods
- Results
- Discussion

Inclusion of specific review of theories in the Introduction section to present theoretical evidences as the basic theories or empirical evidences that review the previous studies is allowed. At this stage, the basic organization of the research article would appear as:

First section

- Title
- Author(s)
- Abstract
- Keywords

The body

1. INTRODUCTION
2. LITARTURE REVIEW
3. METHODS
4. RESULTS
5. DISCUSSION (or RESULTS AND DISCUSSION)
6. CONCLUSION

Closing section

- ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS (optional)
- REFERENCES
- APPENDICES (if any)

Review Article

It is expected that all types of paper cite any relevant literature so this category should only be used if the main purpose of the paper is to annotate and/or critique the literature in a particular subject area. It may be a selective bibliography providing advice on information sources or it may be comprehensive in that the paper's aim is to cover the main contributors to the development of a topic and explore their different views.

The general organization of a review article will appear as ICRED.

Introduction
 Claim
 Reasons
 Evidences
 Discussion

Definitely, a review article will have its organization as follows:

Opening section

Title
 Author(s)
 Abstract
 Keywords

The Body

1. INTRODUCTION
 2. CLAIM
 3. REASONS
 4. EVIDENCES
 5. DISCUSSION
 6. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION
 REFERENCES

General guide to manuscript writing

- Manuscripts **should not be at least 3.500 words and not more than 6,000 words** including references and appendix. Manuscripts that do not adhere to this rule will not be considered for review. Each manuscript must have an abstract **between 100-150 words and 5 key words**.
- Authors are required to send manuscript in word.docx and PDF format.
- To facilitate the blind review process, please ensure that the authors' names do not appear anywhere in the manuscript or in the filename. Authors' names, designations and institutional addresses should be in a separate file.
- Authors are to check manuscripts for accuracy of language before submitting to the journal. The Editorial Board will not edit submitted manuscripts for style or language.
- Papers submitted must not be under consideration for publication elsewhere, either in electronic or printed form. The corresponding author should declare this when submitting the paper to the Chief Editor.
- Upon submission of a paper, the author/authors are to provide the editorial board with names of three reviewers from different institutions, complete with their addresses, designations and email addresses.

- We do not encourage multiple submissions. An author must publish **ONLY** in alternate issues to other journals. The rule remains in case of co-authorship.
- The Editorial Board reserves the right to make editorial changes to any manuscript accepted for publication to enhance clarity and style.
- Manuscripts that do not adhere to any of the **SUBMISSION GUIDELINES** will not be considered for review.
- An author whose paper is accepted for publication will pay an **Article Publication Charge (APC) IDR 400.000** payable immediately after notification of acceptance has been received.

Technical guide to manuscript writing

- Authors are to submit their paper electronically by using the online submission.
- Authors are required to use the style template format accordingly before submission.
- All manuscripts must be typed in Microsoft Word (.docx) and single-spaced. Margins are to be set at (3 cm at all sides) and paper size at A4 (21 x 29.7cm). **References should be between 10-15% from journals.**
- Authors must make sure that some of the references are current published within the last five years adhering to 10-15% of the total references.
- Authors are required to conform to the References Guidelines (APA style) as given if they want their manuscript to be considered for publication.

REFERENCE STYLE

Text: Citations in the text should follow the referencing style used by the American Psychological Association. You are referred to the Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association, Sixth Edition, ISBN 978-1-4338-0561-5, copies of which may be ordered online or APA Order Dept., P.O.B. 2710, Hyattsville, MD 20784, USA or APA, 3 Henrietta Street, London, WC3E 8LU, UK.

List: references should be arranged first alphabetically and then further sorted chronologically if necessary. More than one reference from the same author(s) in the same year must be identified by the letters 'a', 'b', 'c', etc., placed after the year of publication.

Citation of authors

If there are two authors, cited paper should be written in this way (Hartmann & James, 2001).

Cite papers with one author and two authors in this manner (Atkins, 1996; Leech & Nesi, 1999).

Follow this format if you cite a secondary source (Lemmens & Wekker, 1990 as cited in de Schryver, 2003).

Journal Publication

Van der Geer, J., Hanraads, J. A. J., & Lupton, R. A. (2010). The art of writing a scientific article. *Journal of Scientific Communications*, 163, 51–59.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.Sc.2010.00372>.

Reference to a journal publication with a DOI

Caifen Chen. (2017). A case study on the relationship between individual differences and English pragmatic competence of non-English major Chinese postgraduate. *English Linguistics Research*. Vol. 6 No. 1, pp. 58-73.
 DOI: 10.5430/elr.v6n1p56.

Reference to a book:

Ellis, R. (2003). *Task-based Language Learning and Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. (Chapter 4).

Reference to a chapter in an edited book:

Kachru, B.B. (2006). World Englishes and culture war. In B.B. Kachru, Y. Kachru & C. L. Nelson (Eds.). *The handbook of world Englishes* (pp. 446-472). Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.

Reference to a website:

Cancer Research UK. Cancer statistics reports for the UK. (2003).
<http://www.cancerresearchuk.org/aboutcancer/statistics/cancerstatsreport/>
 Accessed 13 March 2003.

For newspaper articles (non-authored)

Newspaper (year), "Article title", date, pages. e.g. *The Jakarta Post*. (2018), "Politics and Democracy", 2 February, p. 7.

For encyclopedia entries (with no author or editor)

Title of Encyclopedia (year) "Title of entry", volume, edition, Title of Encyclopedia, Publisher, Place of publication, pages.

e.g. *Encyclopaedia Britannica* (1926) "Psychology of culture contact", Vol. 1, 13th ed., Encyclopaedia Britannica, London and New York, NY, pp. 765-71.

Internet Source

Faizah Abdul Majid, Zalizan Jelas & Norzaini Azman. (2002). *Selected Malaysian Adult Learners' Academic Reading Strategies: A Case Study*. Retrieved August 16, 2005 from <http://face.stir.ac.uk/Majidp61.htm>

Proceedings

Wang, Y. & Le, T. (2011). *Teaching, learning and management: A case study of intercultural communication and education*. AARE 2006 Conference Proceedings, 27-30 November, Adelaide EJ ISSN 1324-9339 (2007).

Reference to a conference paper

Engle, E.K., Cash, T.F., & Jarry, J.L. (2009, November). *The Body Image Behaviours Inventory-3: Development and validation of the Body Image Compulsive Actions and Body Image Avoidance Scales*. Poster session presentation at the meeting of the Association for Behavioural and Cognitive Therapies, New York, NY.

Thesis or Dissertation

Ngoc Minh Vu. (2017). *Teaching pragmatic in English as a Foreign Language at a Vietnamese university: Teachers' perceptions, curricular content, and classroom practices*. Unpublished Ph.D' Dissertation. Sydney: Faculty of Educational and Social Work, University of Sydney.

PAPER TEMPLATE

Title of Paper
(Times new roman, font size 13, not more than 10 words)

First author's name
Institution or University
Address
Current e-mail address
Times New Roman font 12

Second author's name
Institution or University
Current e-mail address
Times New Roman font 12

Abstract

Insert your abstract here following this structure: Introduction, Methods, Results and Implication. Use Times New Roman font size 12. Abstract should be 150-200 words and in one paragraph only. An abstract must be fully self-contained, capsule description of the paper, and meet the word count limitation.

Keywords: 5 keywords separated by a comma {,}

1. INTRODUCTION (12 font)

Use Times New Roman font 12 and single spacing for texts in a paragraph. Paragraphs are justified. It introduces the research background, issues and logics why this study was undertaken, and defines what was the research questions, the hypothesis to be tested or the purposes of the research. The introduction requires a short review of the literature pertaining to the research topic, starting with broad topics and slowly focusing at the work at hand described at around four paragraphs. One to two paragraphs introduce the reader to the general field of the study. The subsequent paragraphs describe how an aspect of this field could be improved. The final paragraph is critical, it clearly states in the first sentence of the paragraph the research questions that the research will answer. The entire introduction should logically end at the research questions and thesis statements or hypothesis. A summary sentence may be added stating how the answer of your question will contribute to the overall of the study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature review is a critical summary, classification, and evaluation of existing theory and research on your topics. It addresses a specific and well-defined questions

or set of questions, that outlines the background and history of your research problems, identifies possible methods for your study, assess the strengths and weaknesses of previous studies, provide a conceptual framework and rationale of your study. Literature review is not a laundry list of studies. You should primarily draw evidence from peer-review journals as the primary sources and books as the secondary sources. It is not the place to express your opinion or point of view, so all statements should be drawn from cited work. Literature review might be integrated in the introduction section before research questions are defined, or it is presented in a separate Literature Review section.

3. METHODS

No spacing between paragraphs. Next paragraphs indent (No spacing). Method section describes: when, where and how was the study done. What materials were used or who was included in the study. The description includes: approach/context of the study, participants, instrument, procedures, data analysis techniques. Method section should be straightforward description of the methods used in your study. Each method should be described in a separate section. Begin in a single section with a statement of the materials used in this study so that readers have the capability to repeat the work in their own intention. Next, describe in separate sections each key procedure and technique used in the study. Keep the explanation brief and concise. Write the method section in the past form. Passive voices are probably most appropriate.

4. RESULTS

Result section is presented in adherence to the research questions. It presents the main data and the results of data analysis. An interpretation and discussion should not be inserted in the result section. You should provide an overview of primary results at the first section, and flow the results in a step-by-step fashion. This overview should follow directly the data analysis plan stated in the method. It requires you fully describe the results of data analysis so that readers can gauge how the findings of your study answer the research questions. Then, present primarily findings followed by any secondary and subgroup findings. Use table, figures or excerpts, such as citation or quotation from interview data, to demonstrate the characteristics of major findings. Avoid redundancy between text, tables, figures, or excerpts.

5. DISCUSSION (or Results and Discussion)

Discussion section might be called as Discussion or Summary of Findings. Discussion section consists of three parts: addressing the hypothesis, problems and limitations, and closing the closing. The purpose is to highlight the major findings from the results section and interpret them. Restate the overall purposes of the study in this section. Then, explain the main findings from the results section. Explain how the findings relate to the purpose of the study, taking into account each research question. Also describe how the results are related to education in general. Discussion section does not need to include any raw data, and statistics. Simply explain the results in language that is easy for a non-researcher to understand. Also

try to integrate the findings into the results of other studies you have cited in the literature review.

6. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

In conclusion section, briefly summarize the overall conclusion of the data analysis based on the purposes of the study. Explain the important of the major findings to educational practice. Typically, in conclusion section the author should: summarize and conclude the results of analysis by restating the main argument, and presenting key conclusions and recommendation; state how the finding applies to the world of practice; state what are the implication for further research; say to what extend your original questions have been answered; and state the limitations of your research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT (Optional)

If you received any significant helps in thinking up, designing or carrying out the work, or received materials of funding from someone who did you a favor by supplying them, you must acknowledge their assistance and the services or materials provided. Place any acknowledgement here. We would like to thank xxxxxxxx.

REFERENCE (Examples)

[10-15% of references are journal articles]

Primary sources cited from journals must take place 10-15% of overall references in your journal. Proceeding articles, seminar papers, and book references follow. Use APA style for the citation format.

Sections and sub-sections are presented in adherence to the following categories:

1. FIRST LEVEL SUB-HEADING (All Capital Letter, Font 12)

No spacing between paragraphs. Next paragraphs indent. Use numbers in headings and sub-headings.

1.1. Second Level Subheading (First word capitalized, Font 12)

No spacing between paragraphs. Next paragraphs indent (No spacing).

1.1.1. Third Level Subheading (First word capitalized, *Italic*, Font 12)

No spacing between paragraphs. Next paragraphs indent (No spacing).

Tables

You can refer to tables in this way: Table 1, 2, 3, 4 and so on.

Refer to Table 1 first, then only insert Table 1 below the text or paragraph (as shown).

Table 1. Insert title of Table 1 (Font 11)

Heading (Font size = 10)	Heading (Font size = 10)	Heading (Font size = 10)
Content (Font size = 10)	Content (Font size = 10)	Content (Font size = 10)
Content (Font size = 10)	Content (Font size = 10)	Content (Font size = 10)
Content (Font size = 10)	Content (Font size = 10)	Content (Font size = 10)
Content (Font size = 10)	Content (Font size = 10)	Content (Font size = 10)

Figure

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Figure 1. Insert title of Figure 1. The title of Figure 1 must be below the figure (Font 10)